

ADVISORY GUIDELINES FOR BREAST CANCER SURVIVORS

REBECCA

Research on breast cancer induced chronic conditions
supported by causal analysis of multi-source data

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A. Guidelines and Advice on Diet for Breast Cancer Survivors

	Guidelines for cancer survivors
D1	Increased intake of wholegrains and legumes
D2	Increased intake of vegetables and fruits
D3	Limitation of consumption of "fast food" and other processed foods high in fat, starch, or sugars
D4	Limitation of consumption of red meats (maximum 3 portions of 140g cooked red meat/week) and avoid processed meats
D5	Avoidance of sugary drink consumption
	Limited evidence for breast cancer survivors
D6	Consume foods that contain soy (2 mg/day of isoflavone)

References:

<https://www.wcrf.org/diet-activity-and-cancer/global-cancer-update-programme/cancer-survivors/>

<https://www.wcrf.org/diet-activity-and-cancer/global-cancer-update-programme/cancer-survivors/breast-cancer-survivors-and-mortality-risk/>

<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/ijc.34321#ijc34321-bib-0075>

<https://www.wcrf-uk.org/health-advice-and-support/living-with-cancer/eat-well-during-cancer/can-i-eat-meat-if-i-have-or-have-had-cancer/>

	Examples of advice
<p>D3 + D1</p>	<p><u>Observation</u></p> <p><i>Based on your food log we/I notice that you consume fast foods quite often (can be specific times per week/month). It is important to reduce its intake as it tends to be high in unhealthy fats, starches, and sugars.</i></p> <p><u>Advice</u></p> <p><i>We/I would suggest when craving fast food, to opt for options like grilled chicken or fish, whole-grain buns, wraps, and plenty of vegetables. Ideally, if you have the time and the energy prepare homemade meals using fresh ingredients and lean proteins (e.g., avocado toast, pizza with whole grain wrap and fresh vegetables, etc) (D3).</i></p> <p><i>Besides reducing the fast food, it would be beneficial to try to increase the consumption of whole grains and legumes. These foods provide essential fiber, vitamins, minerals, and other nutrients that are crucial for the proper functioning of your body and there is evidence suggesting that fiber-rich foods may reduce the risk of mortality (D1).</i></p> <p><i>You can try including into your diet foods like oats, whole wheat bread, lentils, or beans daily. Some examples of how you can incorporate them into your meals are: a bowl of porridge with oats for breakfast, a lentil salad for lunch, and a whole grain avocado toast for dinner. You can also increase your legume consumption by adding them to soups, stews, wraps, or salads. When choosing whole grains and legumes, remember to check the fiber content on food labels and aim for approximately 25-30 grams of fiber per day (D1).</i></p>

D2	<p><u>Observation</u></p> <p>Based on your food log we/I see that your fruit and vegetable consumption is lower than the recommended (5 portions per day; the protioning can be avoided, as it is not something easy to identify)</p> <p><u>Advice</u></p> <p>Let´s try to include more colourful vegetables and fruits into your meals. Some vegetables that you can add as a side in your main meals or in your salads, sandwiches, or wraps are broccoli, spinach, bell peppers, carrots, or sweet potatoes. Some fruits are berries, oranges, apples, bananas, or kiwis and can be enjoyed as snacks or added to your breakfast or salads.</p>
D3	<p><u>Observation</u></p> <p>Based on your food log we/I notice that you consume processed foods and sugary snacks frequently.</p> <p><u>Advice</u></p> <p>These foods are high in unhealthy additives, and it is recommended to limit their intake. Instead of processed snacks, you can choose nutritious alternatives like fresh or dried fruits (without sugar), raw nuts, Greek yogurt with berries, or homemade mix of nuts and dried fruits or root-fruits.</p>
D4 + D1	<p><u>Observation</u></p> <p>Based on your food log we/I see that you have red meat almost every day and you consume regularly processed meats such as bacon, ham, or salami during the week.</p> <p><u>Advice</u></p> <p>It would be beneficial to limit the red meat consumption (maximum 3 portions of 140g cooked red meat/week) and choose leaner protein sources like poultry (chicken or turkey), fish, or plant-based proteins (tofu, tempeh, Quorn or legumes) instead. To achieve that you can start by having smaller portions of red meat and try keeping some days meat-free (D4) (a feasible strategy might be to define specific meat-free days as the first step, E.g., introduce "Green-Tuesday")</p>

	<p><i>Regarding process meats, there is no safe amount of consumption, and it is recommended to avoid them altogether, as they can be high in unhealthy additives and have been associated with adverse health effects, particularly for cancer survivors. You can replace processed meats with healthier protein sources such as hard-boiled eggs, grilled chicken or turkey breast, salmon, canned tuna in spring water, low-fat hummus, cream cheese or plant-based alternatives like seitan or tofu (D4).</i></p> <p><i>A good plant-based substitute of red meat are legumes (beans, lentils, chickpeas). A tip to increase their consumption is to add them to soups, stews, wraps, or salads. You can also make "legume balls" instead of meatballs with chickpeas (falafel), beans or lentils. When choosing legumes, remember to check the fiber content on food labels and aim for approximately 25-30 grams of fiber per day (D1).</i></p>
D5	<p><u>Observation</u></p> <p><i>Your food log shows a significant intake of sugary drinks.</i></p> <p><u>Advice</u></p> <p><i>It's important to be mindful of these beverages as they can lead to increased sugar consumption and potential health issues. It's best to opt for healthier drink options like water, herbal tea, or unsweetened beverages. Try water infused with fresh fruits like lemon, lime, or berries for a refreshing and flavourful twist!) (one still debated point amongst nutritionists is the appropriateness of sugary-free substitutes of sugary drinks in nutritional advising – e.g., cola zero. We have no issues with this, and can also be considered. However, this might not be acceptable by the whole nutritional science domain and there might also be challenges for the general public to accept this)</i></p>
D6	<p><u>Advice</u></p> <p><i>There is some limited evidence suggesting that consuming soy foods may have benefits for breast cancer survivors. Try including moderate amounts of soy foods in your diet, such as tofu, tempeh, edamame, and soy milk. Check the content of these foods in isoflavones from the food labels and aim for approximately 2mg/day of isoflavones from these sources.</i></p>

B. Guidelines and Advice on Physical Activity for Breast Cancer Survivors

	Guidelines
PA1	150 - 300 min of MIAPA (moderate-intensity aerobic physical activity) OR at least 75–150 min VIAPA (vigorous-intensity aerobic physical activity) per week
PA2	2 days per week muscle-strengthening
PA3	3 days per week balance and strength training
PA4	Limit sedentary time and replace it with physical activity of any intensity (including light intensity)

References:

<https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/physical-activity>

	Examples of advice
PA1	<p><u>Observation</u></p> <p><i>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard we/I noticed you engaged in more than 100 min, moderate-intensity aerobic activity last week.</i></p> <p><u>Advice</u></p> <p><i>It's great! Let's aim to gradually increase it to 150 minutes. You can do that by engaging in activities like brisk walking, cycling, or swimming. (as a rule, the specific circumstances for each individual should be considered when providing this advice. Age, mobility and physical capabilities are important and should be considered. The living environment should also be taken in to consideration. One interventonal strategy can be to identify what type of aerobic exercise does the patient already do and try to increase the duration incrementally).</i></p>
	<p><u>Observation</u></p> <p><i>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard we/I see that you engaged in 60 minutes of vigorous-intensity aerobic activity last week.</i></p> <p><u>Advice</u></p> <p><i>Fantastic effort! Can we work towards reaching at least 75 minutes per week? Activities like running, dancing, or playing a sport (again, identify what is already present and built on that) that get your heart rate up can help you reach this goal. Do you need help to explore new options or overcome any challenges you might face?</i></p>

PA2	<p><u>Observation</u></p> <p><i>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard we/I noticed you completed one muscle-strengthening session at the gym last week.</i></p> <p><u>Advice</u></p> <p><i>That's a good start! Research suggests doing these exercises twice a week for stronger bones, increased muscle mass, weight control and joint flexibility. If you do not enjoy weightlifting, you can incorporate into your training routine activities like resistance training or bodyweight exercises. Remember: exercises with elastic bands can be a good way to introduce such exercises for older individuals</i></p>
PA3	<p><u>Observation</u></p> <p><i>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard we/I noticed you didn't perform any balance and strength training sessions last week.</i></p> <p><u>Advice</u></p> <p><i>We/I want to emphasize the importance of incorporating these sessions into your training routine. They play a key role in maintaining stability, supporting your joints, and reducing the risk of falls. How about trying one session this week? We can explore different options that suit your preferences and needs, such as yoga, tai chi, or specific balance training routines. These exercises can be enjoyable and beneficial for your physical health. As you progress, let's aim to gradually increase the number of sessions to three per week. This will help you build strength, improve balance, and enhance your overall stability. Remember, it's about finding a pace that works for you and fits into your lifestyle.</i></p>
PA4	<p><u>Observation</u></p>

	<p>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard we/I noticed there were long periods of sedentary time in your daily routine.</p> <p><u>Advice</u></p> <p>Let's aim to reduce this by replacing it with physical activity of any intensity every day. Even light-intensity movements, such as stretching, taking short walks, or doing household chores, can be beneficial. Remember, every step counts towards a healthier you! Introduction of very small walks at specific time of the day can be a good strategy here. E.g., identify usual time at home from the REBECCA dashboard and help the patient to introduce a small walk in the middle of the most pronounced sedentary period. In practice, concerning PA, this might be the main type of advice/intervention that REBECCA will support (and it is an important one!!!)</p>
<p>PA4 + RSI1&3</p>	<p><u>Observation</u></p> <p>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard we/I noticed that you spend long periods of time sitting and rarely leave your home.</p> <p><u>Advice:</u></p> <p>Let's try to change that and incorporate some physical activity into your daily routine. It doesn't have to be intense exercise. Even simple movements like stretching, short walks, or doing household chores can be helpful (PA4). Additionally, spending a lot of time at home can limit your social interactions, which are vital for your mental and emotional well-being. It is important to leave home and spend time out with your loved ones, engaging in activities that make you happy. It's not just about physical health but also your emotional well-being. Connecting with others and having a support system can make a positive difference in how you feel (RSI1 & 3).</p>

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So, let's try to increase your physical activity and decrease the amount of time you spend at home. Take short walks in your neighbourhood and look for chances to go out and spend time with friends and family. It's all about finding a balance and taking care of yourself!

C. Guidelines and Advice on Sleep for Breast Cancer Survivors

	Guidelines
S1	General guideline: Sleeping Well
S2	Sleep at least 7 hours a night
S3	Quality of sleep is also important
S4	A regular sleep pattern is crucial for achieving a restful and high-quality sleep

References:

<https://www.cdc.gov/cancer/survivors/healthy-living-guides/physical-health/sleep.htm>

	Examples of advice
S1+S2+ S3+S4	<p><u>Observation:</u></p> <p>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard we/I noticed that:</p> <p>You are struggling to get 7 hours of sleep every day/ you are experiencing challenges in falling asleep (>30 min) / you are waking up multiple times during the night (more than once)/ it takes a while for you to fall back asleep after waking up (>20 min).</p> <p><u>Advice:</u></p> <p>Here are some tips that may help you:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To support your sleep, try to spend at least 15 minutes outdoors in the morning to soak up natural sunlight, which helps regulate your sleep hormone melatonin. 2. Establishing a consistent sleep routine is vital. Aim to go to bed and wake up at the same time every day, including weekends, to train your body's internal clock for better sleep. 3. Prioritize winding down before bedtime. Engage in relaxing activities like reading a book or taking a warm bath to calm your mind and prepare your body for a restful sleep. 4. Create an ideal sleep environment in your bedroom. Ensure it is quiet, dark, relaxing, and set at a comfortable temperature to promote a peaceful and uninterrupted night's sleep. 5. Improve your sleep hygiene by keeping electronic devices like TVs, computers, and smartphones out of the bedroom. This will reduce distractions and promote a more restful sleep. 6. To optimize your sleep, avoid consuming large meals, caffeine, and alcohol close to bedtime. Instead, opt for light, sleep-friendly snacks (e.g., banana, almond, yoghurt) and beverages (e.g., chamomile or valerian tea, warm milk) to support a more tranquil sleep. 7. Incorporating regular physical activity into your day can positively impact your sleep. Engage in moderate exercise, such as walking or yoga, to facilitate falling asleep more easily at night.

RSI4
+
S2&3

Observation

Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard, we/I noticed that **it takes you over an hour and a half to fall asleep each night, resulting in less than 7 hours of sleep**. Furthermore, we/I observed from your online activity that you tend to spend **too much time on your phone late at night**, and the data from your wearable device indicates that you consume **significant amounts of food before going to sleep**.

Advice

We/I would recommend you make some lifestyle modifications that will improve your sleep and your overall health. First of all, eating a lot before bedtime can disrupt your sleep. When you eat a lot, especially late at night, your body must work on digesting the food instead of getting the rest it needs. This can make it harder for you to fall asleep and get the deep sleep you need. To help with this, we/I recommend having your last meal at least three hours before going to bed **(RSI4)**. If you feel hungry later, go for light and sleep-friendly snacks like a banana, some almonds, or yogurt. You can also try sleep-promoting beverages like chamomile or valerian tea, or warm milk **(S2&3)**. Lastly, using your phone before sleep does not help you relax and prepare for a good night's sleep. Therefore, try to keep all the electronic devices out of the room when going to sleep, and instead of using your mobile try reading a book or taking a warm bath **(S2&3)**.

D. Guidelines and Advice on Alcohol Use for Breast Cancer Survivors

	Guidelines
A1	Avoid or reduce alcohol intake (1 or less drinks per day).

References: <https://www.cdc.gov/cancer/alcohol/index.htm>

	Examples of advice
A1	<p><u>Observation</u></p> <p><i>Based on the pictures you have uploaded in the REBECCA app we/I noticed that you consume on average 5 alcoholic drinks per week.</i></p> <p><u>Advice</u></p> <p><i>Alcohol consumption can negatively affect your body's ability to heal and increases the chances of cancer recurrence. Additionally, it may interfere with your recovery, and it can also increase the risk of developing a new primary cancer. For these reasons it is advisable to limit (one drink or less in a day) or avoid alcohol consumption. Do you think you can reduce your alcohol consumption? Would you need help in finding ways to do it?</i></p>

	<p><i>Why Does Alcohol Use Raise Cancer Risk?</i></p> <p><i>When you drink alcohol, your body breaks it down into a chemical called acetaldehyde. Acetaldehyde damages your DNA and prevents your body from repairing the damage. DNA is the cell's "instruction manual" that controls a cell's normal growth and function. When DNA is damaged, a cell can begin growing out of control and create a cancer tumor.</i></p>

E. Guidelines and Advice on Tobacco Use for Breast Cancer Survivors

	Guidelines
T1	Avoid tobacco use

References:

<https://www.cdc.gov/cancer/survivors/health-care-providers/tobacco-use.htm>

https://cancercontrol.cancer.gov/sites/default/files/2022-07/Mon23_FactSheet_508.pdf

	Examples of advice
T1	<p><u>Observation</u></p> <p><i>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard and the data from your wearable device we/I see that you continue smoking.</i></p> <p><u>Advice</u></p> <p><i>We/I understand that quitting smoking can be extremely challenging, but as a breast cancer survivor, it's important to recognize the significant benefits it brings to your health and well-being. Quitting smoking is one of the most effective ways to improve your chances of survival, enhance your quality of life, and maintain good overall health. Smoking weakens your immune system, leaving you more susceptible to infections. Additionally, studies indicate that breast cancer</i></p>

	<p>survivors who smoke face a higher risk of mortality from cancer-related causes and have an increased risk of developing a new primary cancer. Quitting smoking greatly reduces this risk, enhances your response to breast cancer treatment and minimizes complications. Finally, it strengthens your body's natural defences, reduces the risk of severe infections, and improves your long-term survival. Do you think you can try quitting smoking? Would you need help in finding ways to do it?</p>
<p>T1 + A1 + RSI1&3 + PA4</p>	<p>Observation:</p> <p>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard and the pictures uploaded in the REBECCA app, we/I noticed that you are smoking, consuming alcohol, and spending a significant amount of time at home lately.</p> <p>Advice:</p> <p>As a breast cancer survivor, it is necessary to prioritize your overall well-being and take steps to minimize any factors that may increase the risk of cancer recurrence or hinder your recovery. We/I would like to provide you with some advice regarding the concerns raised by your current lifestyle.</p> <p>First of all, smoking poses significant health risks and is associated with various types of cancer, including breast cancer. It is strongly recommended that you quit smoking to improve your health and reduce the likelihood of cancer recurrence. If you feel that you need help to do it, there are numerous resources available to support you in this journey, such as smoking cessation programs that I can recommend (T1).</p> <p>Secondly, alcohol consumption can have negative effects on your body's ability to heal and increase the chances of cancer recurrence. It may also interfere with your recovery process and increase the risk of developing new primary cancers. Try to avoid or limit your alcohol intake to one drink or less per day. I understand that reducing or eliminating alcohol may be challenging, but I think that it is worth making the effort (A1).</p> <p>Lastly, spending a lot of time at home limits your physical activity and may also limit your social interactions, which are essential for maintaining a healthy lifestyle. Regular exercise, (even small walks in your neighbourhood) can improve your physical and mental well-being, boost your immune system, and reduce the risk of cancer recurrence (PA4). Also, don't forget the importance of spending time with friends and family, engaging in activities that bring you joy, and connecting</p>

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with others. Building strong social connections can provide you with emotional support, make you feel less alone, and have a positive impact on your well-being (RSI1&3)!

You have already shown great strength in battling breast cancer, and I am sure you can make these lifestyle changes that will further enhance your health and well-being!

F. Guidelines and Advice on Anxiety and Distress for Breast Cancer Survivors

	Guidelines
AD1	Stress and anxiety can have a negative effect on breast cancer survivors' quality of life.
AD2	Anger can have a negative effect on breast cancer survivors' quality of life.
AD3	Loneliness can have a negative effect on breast cancer survivors' quality of life.

References:

<https://www.cdc.gov/cancer/survivors/healthy-living-guides/emotional-health/common-feelings.htm>

	Examples of advice
AD1	<p><u>Observation</u></p> <p>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard and your online activity, we/I noticed that you've been dealing with a lot of stress lately.</p> <p><u>Advice</u></p> <p>We/I want you to know that I'm here to provide guidance and support as we explore strategies together to help you find relief from the overwhelming stress you're facing. Some simple advice is:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. When you are feeling stressed, try going for a short walk or engaging in any form of exercise to help reduce tension and boost your mood. Introducing specific exercise sequences (e.g., easy to do yoga stances) for stress management can be a good idea. These should be short, as the goal is not PA increase, but rather stress management 2. Consider setting aside a few minutes each day for meditation or using relaxation apps/videos to help quiet your mind and promote a sense of calm. 3. Engaging in creative pursuits like painting, dancing, playing music, writing, or doing crafts can provide a therapeutic outlet and help you alleviate stress. The specific individual characteristics should be considered. 4. Connecting with fellow breast cancer survivors through support groups or online communities can offer an opportunity to share your feelings and gain insights from others who have experienced similar challenges. The different centers should make sure to have already identified such groups in each city/community. E.g., Amazonas for Stockholm.
AD2	<p><u>Observation</u></p> <p>Based on what your companion has reported it seems that you are lately more angry than usual</p> <p><u>Advice</u></p>

	<p><i>It's normal to feel angry after treatment for a lot of reasons. The diagnosis itself, a bad experience with a doctor, or an unsupportive friend or relative. These feelings may go away over time as you settle into your new routine. We/I want to share with you some tips that may help to alleviate your anger.</i></p> <p><i>First of all, it is important to ask yourself what's causing your anger and what you can do about it. Answering these questions and talking about how you're feeling can help you manage your anger. Another thing that can help, is to focus on what you can control. Being involved in your health care, keeping your appointments, making changes in your lifestyle, or even setting your daily schedule are things you can control. When you feel more in control, you're less likely to feel frustrated and angry. It is also effective to find ways to calm your temper. You can learn ways to redirect angry feelings and reframe your thoughts to alleviate anger and feel calmer. Finally, sometimes the best way to cope with anger is to join a cause. For example, becoming a cancer advocate could help give purpose and meaning to your experience.</i></p>
AD3	<p><u>Observation</u></p> <p><i>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard and the reports from the companion app, we/I have noticed that you have been showing signs of isolation and loneliness lately. It seems that you prefer to stay home, have not been joining the patient support meetings the last month and it has been a long time since you last met up with your friends.</i></p> <p><u>Advice</u></p> <p><i>After treatment, it's easy to feel cut off from other people who may not understand what you're going through. And that's normal. You can consider joining support groups (in person or online) since it is a great way to meet with other survivors to share feelings, concerns, and journeys to a "new normal." Additionally, it would be helpful to have open conversations with your loved ones about your concerns, fears, and thoughts. Communicating your needs and concerns will not only make you feel better, but it will help them understand how you feel and help you.</i></p>
A1 + S4	<p><u>Observation</u></p> <p><i>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard we/I notice that you consume a lot of alcohol particularly late at night and it takes you more than an hour to fall asleep every night. Considering this data, along with the content of your online activity, it seems like you have been experiencing high levels of stress lately.</i></p>

+ AD1 + PA1&3	<p><u>Advice</u></p> <p><i>We/I would recommend you make some lifestyle adjustments that will improve your overall mental and physical health and the effectiveness of your treatment. You can start by trying to decrease the alcohol consumption to one drink or less per day since it has a negative impact on your body's ability to recover and increases the chances of cancer recurrence (A1). It is also important to make an effort to go to bed and wake up at the same time every day, including weekends to be able to have a better sleep (S4). The quality of your sleep will improve, and you will feel less anxious if you engage in moderate intensity exercises like brisk walking, cycling, or calming activities like yoga and Pilates (PA1&3). To further reduce your anxiety, try practicing meditation for 5-15 minutes each day. Finally, to quiet your mind and foster a sense of calm you can try using relaxation apps or videos (AD1).</i></p>
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Reference for physical activity (PA1&3):

Vijayvergia N, Denlinger CS. Lifestyle Factors in Cancer Survivorship: Where We Are and Where We Are Headed. J Pers Med. 2015 Jul 2;5(3):243-63. doi: 10.3390/jpm5030243. PMID: 26147495; PMCID: PMC4600146.

G.Rebecca-specific indicators for Breast Cancer Survivors

	Rebecca specific indicators
RSI1	Daily mobility
RSI2	Working after treatment
RSI3	Relationships and support systems
RSI4	Eating behaviours (eating rate and portions)

References:

<https://www.cancervic.org.au/get-support/living-with-cancer/life-after-treatment/living-well-after-cancer>

<https://www.cancervic.org.au/downloads/resources/booklets/Living-Well-After-Cancer.pdf>

<https://www.cancervic.org.au/get-support/cancer-services/service-types/sexuality-and-intimacy-service-type.html>

<https://www.cancervic.org.au/get-support/work/cancer-and-work/cancer-work-and-you>

	Examples of advice
RSI1 + RSI3	<p><u>Observation</u></p> <p><i>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard and the reports from the companion app, we/I have noticed that you have been showing signs of isolation and loneliness lately. It seems that you prefer to stay home, have not been joining the patient support meetings the last month and it has been a long time since you last met up with your friends.</i></p> <p><u>Advice</u></p> <p><i>We/I completely understand that what you are going through is not easy and you may feel that you want to be alone. And that's fine. We/I just want to remind you that spending time outside of home with your friends and family, engaging in activities that bring you joy, will make you feel better and have a positive impact on your overall well-being (RSI1). We/I would encourage you to have open conversations with your partner about your concerns, fears, and thoughts. Communicating with your loved ones your needs and concerns will not only make you feel better, but it will help them understand how you feel and help you. Lastly, you can seek couples or family counselling, consult specialists or counsellors, or connect with support groups to navigate the changes and challenges you face and provide guidance and support (RSI3).</i></p>
RSI2	<p><u>Observation</u></p> <p><i>Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard, we/I have noticed that you have concerns about returning to work.</i></p> <p><u>Advice</u></p> <p><i>We/I understanding that going back to work may seem difficult and stressful right now, but we/I would like to share with you some advice to make your transition back to work smoother. First of all, it is important to set realistic goals and not to put yourself undue pressure to perform at the same level as before your treatment. It would be helpful to have a gradual transition back to work and not to start working immediately full-time. You can start working part-time or with a modified</i></p>

schedule to adjust to the new circumstances and monitor your energy levels and overall well-being. To keep your energy levels up, prioritize your self-care by planning breaks during the day, using stress-relieving methods, maintaining a balanced diet, exercising frequently, and making sure you receive enough sleep. You can also discuss with your employer about your treatment journey and your needs or any adjustments that can facilitate a smooth transition back to work. Finally, try creating a network of support in the workplace by discuss your experiences with co-workers or managers you can trust. This will create a supportive atmosphere and will help you feel less stress.

Observation

*Based on the REBECCA behavioural dashboard, we/I have noticed that you tend to **eat your meals quickly and consume large portions of food.***

Advice

Eating fast and a lot, can lead to weight gain, indigestion and upset stomach, insulin resistance and other health problems. As a breast cancer survivor, it's important to maintain a healthy weight and adop eating habits that can support your body's healing process.

RSI4

In order to eat your meals at a slower pace, try taking small bites and chew thoroughly. Take your time to enjoy the flavours and put your fork down between each bite. Aim to eat your meal for at least 20 minutes (or longer). Before eating, take a few deep breaths or perform a quick relaxation exercise. This can help you become more mindful of your hunger and satiety cues. Eat always sitting down in the table and avoid eating in front of the TV, scrolling on your phone, while driving or when you are stressed. Try to enjoy your food with family or friends whenever you can.

In order to reduce the amount of food you consume without feeling deprived, serve your meals in smaller plates or bowls. Remember to start your meal with a salad or a serving of vegetables, to feel fuller and to prevent overeating during the main course. Another tip is to drink water before and during your meal because sometimes our bodies mistake thirst for

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hunger, leading to unnecessary eating. Finally, avoiding distractions as I already mention can help you being aware of the quantity of food you consume.

